

The Influence of Capital Structure, ESG (Environmental, Social, And Governance), And Firm Size on Financial Performance of Food & Beverage Subsector Companies Listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2019-2023

Verawati¹, FX Kurniawan Tjakrawala²

^{1,2} Study program of Accountant Profesion (PPAK), Business & Economic Faculty, Tarumanagara University
Jl. Tanjung Duren Utara No.1, DKI Jakarta, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study examines the impact of Capital Structure, ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance), and Company Size on Financial Performance in Food & Beverage Subsector Companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2019 to 2023. Using a quantitative approach, it analyzes secondary data from 95 companies, with 23 meeting the sample criteria. Panel data regression was tested using Microsoft Excel and E-Views Series 9. The findings indicate that (1) Capital Structure does not affect Financial Performance; (2) ESG has a positive and significant effect; (3) Company Size negatively affects Financial Performance; and (4) all three variables collectively have a positive and significant impact to Financial Performance.

KEYWORDS: Capital Structure, Company Size, and Environmental, Food & Beverage Companies, Financial Performance, Social, and Governance (ESG)

I. INTRODUCTION

Companies are encouraged to continuously adapt their strategies to respond to environmental changes by expanding into unexplored business areas and enhancing trade. Understanding consumer needs, preferences, and market trends is crucial for optimizing performance and generating profits (Jao et al., 2022). Profitability serves as a key indicator of a company's success over a specific period. Effective management and financial analysis are essential in assessing performance, with financial statements providing crucial insights into an organization's stability and commitment (Mahdi & Rahmawati, 2023; Senastri, 2023). Rombe & Sintha (2023) state that financial reports reflect a company's ability to achieve performance targets. Financial performance indicates a company's achievements over a given period, encompassing financial conditions based on capital, liquidity, and profitability (Aprilianti & Sisdianto, 2024). However, financial statements are vulnerable to fraud (Pertiwi et al., 2023). To attract investors, companies often present the best available information, creating opportunities for manipulation. Accurate accounting data is vital for capital market decision-making.

Table I. Profit Growth Rate 2019 – 2023

Year	Profit Growth (%)
2019	7,78
2020	3,94
2021	2,45
2022	3,75
2023	5,33

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics (2025)

The table shows that in 2019, profit growth in the Food and Beverage sector reached 7.78%, but declined to 3.94% in 2020. This downward trend continued until 2021, when profit growth reached its lowest point due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which severely disrupted global economic activity, including in Indonesia. Social restrictions and decreased customer traffic in cafés and restaurants further impacted the sector's financial performance. Despite these challenges, the industry remained a significant

contributor to the manufacturing sector (Humas, 2021). However, factors such as poor budgeting practices also weakened financial performance (Rahman, 2020).

A notable case of financial mismanagement involved PT Tiga Pilar Sejahtera, which was implicated in fund embezzlement and financial report manipulation (Mulia, 2021), highlighting the importance of financial transparency for maintaining stability. The pandemic also significantly affected the Food and Beverage industry, with projected growth of only 4–5% due to shifting consumer priorities (Wijaya et al., 2023). Consumers focused more on essential goods, while demand for many industry products declined. Government regulations restricting outdoor activities further exacerbated the sector's challenges.

Several factors influence a company's financial performance, including capital structure, ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance), and firm size. Capital structure determines the balance between equity and debt, directly affecting profitability (Ngantung & Handoyo, 2023). According to Putri & Raflis (2024), prudent debt management can enhance profits due to tax-deductible interest expenses, but excessive debt increases financial risk. Ningsih & Utami (2020) found that capital structure significantly impacts financial performance. ESG is another crucial factor, promoting operational efficiency and transparency while protecting stakeholders from unethical management practices Agustina et al. (2025). While some studies indicate a negative impact (Laksono & Kusumaningtias, 2021), others highlight its positive influence (Amelinda & Rachmawati, 2021). Firm size also plays a role, with larger companies typically exhibiting greater stability, better capital access, and higher investor interest due to their perceived profitability (Amaliyah & Herwiyanti, 2020; Nilawati & Hendrani, 2024). However, research on this relationship remains inconclusive, with some studies confirming a strong correlation (Injayanti et al., 2020), while others find no significant link (Kurniawati et al., 2020). These findings underscore the complexity of financial performance determinants and the need for effective management strategies. This study aims to empirically examine and verify the impact of several factors on financial performance, including capital structure, ESG, and firm size, both individually and collectively.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Agency Theory

Agency Theory Jensen and Meckling (as cited in Sari, 2022) explain that the relationship between principals (investors) and agents (managers) in corporate decision-making can lead to conflicts of interest due to the separation of ownership and control (Gunawan et al., 2024). Eisenhardt (as cited in Bakti & Triyono, 2022) outlines three fundamental assumptions: individuals act in self-interest (individualism), have limited rational decision-making capabilities (bounded rationality), and tend to avoid risk (risk aversion). Lestari & Widarno (2019) argue that agents' opportunistic behavior may benefit them at the expense of principals. Thus, the theory emphasizes the importance of efficient contracts to reduce conflicts and agency costs (Anggraini et al., 2024). Clear contracts help monitor and control agents' actions through corporate governance mechanisms (Lestari & Purwantini, 2023). Additionally, agency theory supports the implementation of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles to ensure management acts in shareholders' best interests while enhancing transparency and accountability.

B. Signaling Theory

Signaling Theory Spence (1973) in Job Market Signaling describes how management conveys information to investors. Firms with strong performance use financial information as positive signals, whereas poorly performing firms tend to provide less credible signals (Amanda et al., 2019). Management possesses superior knowledge of a company's condition and must disclose information that influences investor decisions. Accounting information, such as financial statements, serves as a key signaling tool (Rahmawati, 2019). Supandi & Goenawan (2023) assert that signaling theory assumes external parties have limited information compared to internal stakeholders, making financial signals crucial. Positive signals from high-performing firms increase investor confidence and stock appreciation. Greater information disclosure enhances investor trust and encourages investment (Wahyuni et al., 2024). Capital structure also acts as a signal; confident management communicates asset, equity, and debt figures to attract investors (Supandi & Goenawan, 2023). Firm size further influences market perception, with larger firms viewed as more stable and capable of generating higher profits (Setyowati & Sari, 2019).

C. Effects of Capital Structure on Financial Performance

Capital structure reflects a firm's financing composition through liabilities and equity, influencing both operational and financial performance (Pertwi, 2024). This ratio determines the proportion of external to internal funds, where a high capital

structure indicates reliance on external financing. Optimal debt utilization enhances operational flexibility, tax efficiency, and investment attractiveness, provided benefits exceed interest costs (Ayem et al., 2023). From a signaling theory perspective, financial obligations signal a firm's stability and prospects to investors. Effective debt management boosts profitability, while poor financial management escalates liabilities, reducing investment appeal (Safitri & Retnani, 2024). Prior studies affirm that funding composition significantly influences financial performance (Pertiwi & Masitoh, 2022). H1: Capital structure affects financial performance.

D. Effects of ESG on Financial Performance

ESG reflects a firm's commitment to sustainability in environmental, social, and governance dimensions, impacting financial outcomes (Buallay, 2019). The environmental aspect covers energy efficiency, carbon emissions, and waste management. Firms adopting strong environmental policies enhance operational efficiency and gain incentives, though green technology investments initially raise costs (Climent, 2018; Husada & Handayani, 2021). The social aspect encompasses workforce welfare and corporate social responsibility (CSR). Companies investing in social aspects foster employee loyalty and competitiveness (Millon et al., 2016), though non-strategic CSR spending may strain finances (Yawika & Handayani, 2019). The governance aspect emphasizes transparency, accountability, and ethical compliance. Strong corporate governance enhances investor trust and financial stability (Khairunnisa & Widiastuty, 2023), whereas governance failures risk scandals and stock value depreciation (Rombe & Sintha, 2023). Strategic ESG implementation strengthens competitiveness and sustainability, though financial impact depends on execution effectiveness. H2: ESG influences financial performance.

E. Effects of ESG on Financial Performance

A firm's valuation—determined by resources, transaction volume, and market capitalization—reflects operational capacity and financial access. Larger firms benefit from economies of scale, cost efficiency, and investment opportunities (Hidayati & Hwihanus, 2025). According to signaling theory, firm size signals managerial capability in investment management and profit generation. Large firms can diversify business operations, mitigating bankruptcy risks compared to smaller firms (Rifiana et al., 2021). Additionally, large firms have stronger competitive advantages due to broader financial resource access, fostering business growth and financial stability. However, greater operational complexity requires efficient management. Research by Injayanti et al. (2020) found that high-valuation firms effectively manage investments and sustain reputations, positively impacting financial performance. H3: Firm size impacts financial performance.

F. Effects of Capital Structure, ESG, and Firm Size on Financial Performance

Resource management effectiveness is reflected in budgeting decisions, influencing corporate stability and investment attractiveness (Ass, 2020; Destiani & Hendriyani, 2021). Investors assess financial performance in investment decisions, necessitating corporate stability maintenance (Destiani & Hendriyani, 2021). Financial performance is jointly influenced by capital structure, ESG, and firm size. An optimal capital structure balancing internal and external financing enhances asset value and overall corporate worth (Suryaningrum & Ratnawati, 2024). Erawati et al. (2022) demonstrated that increased debt proportion positively impacts financial performance. Supervisory boards play a critical role in ESG implementation, ensuring accountability and optimal management, which positively contributes to financial outcomes (Mujiyati, 2020). Audit committees enhance transparency by reinforcing independence (Reni, 2022). Efficient GCG implementation drives financial performance improvements (Hidayat et al., 2021). Firm size determines competitiveness and cost efficiency. Large firms benefit from market power and economies of scale, supporting higher profitability (Jessica & Triyani, 2022). Thus, the combination of an optimal capital structure, strong corporate governance, and large firm size significantly enhances financial performance. H4: Capital structure, ESG, and firm size collectively affect financial performance.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

A. Population and Sample

This study utilizes financial report data from companies in the Food and Beverages sector listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) from 2019 to 2023, with a population of 95 companies and a sample of 23 companies selected through purposive sampling based on specific criteria.

Table II. Research Sample Selection Criteria

No	Criteria	Number of Companies
Population		95
1	Food and Beverages companies not listed on IDX (2019-2023)	(39)
2	Companies not reporting financial statements (2019-2023)	(13)
3	Financial reports not using IDR currency	(2)
4	Companies with consecutive profits (2019-2023)	(18)
Research Sample		23
Total Sample (n x study period)		115

Source: Processed from www.idx.co.id

B. Measurement of Research Variables

The operational aspects and measurement methods used in this study are outlined in the table below:

Table III. Measurement of Dependent and Independent Variables

No	Variable	Formula	Scale	Reference
1	Financial Performance (Y)	$ROA = (\text{Net Income}) / (\text{Total Equity})$	Ratio	Widyaningrum (2024)
2	Capital Structure (X1)	$DER = (\text{Total Debt}) / (\text{Total Equity}) \times 100\%$	Ratio	Lusdani et al. (2024)
3	ESG (X2)	$ESG \text{ Index} = (\text{ESG Disclosure Score}) / (\text{Maximum Disclosure Score}) \times 100\%$	Ratio	Whitelock (2015)
4	Firm Size (X3)	$\text{Size} = \text{Ln}(\text{Total Assets})$	Ratio	Sari & Setyaningsih (2023)

Source: Processed Data (2022)

C. Data Analysis

This study employs panel data regression analysis using Microsoft Excel and E-Views 9. The tests used in this study are descriptive statistics, panel data regression models (Common Effect Model, Fixed Effect Model, and Random Effect Model), model selection tests (Chow test, Hausman test, and Lagrange Multiplier test), classical assumption tests (normality, multicollinearity, heteroskedasticity, and autocorrelation), coefficient of determination (R^2), and hypothesis testing using t-tests and F-tests.

IV. RESULTS

A. Descriptive Statistics

Table IV. Descriptive statistics of all variables

	Y	X1	X2	X3
Mean	9.436.240	0.750676	7.165.217	2.952.847
Median	8.068.074	0.647642	6.000.000	2.915.506
Maximum	4.163.203	2.464.993	1.200.000	3.285.992
Minimum	0.052581	0.102822	3.000.000	2.722.503
Std. Dev.	6.533.893	0.560720	2.106.508	1.462.118
Skewness	1.646.803	1.024.695	0.663317	0.428619
Kurtosis	7.774.680	3.745.214	3.196.591	2.368.338
Jarque-Bera	1.612.176	2.278.604	8.618.310	5.433.044
Probability	0.000000	0.000011	0.013445	0.066104
Sum	1.085.168	8.632.769	8.240.000	3.395.774
Sum Sq. Dev.	4.866.861	3.584.233	5.058.609	2.437.078
Observations	115	115	115	115

Source: Eviews Data Processing (2025)

The table above presents the descriptive statistics for 115 observations from 23 firms over five years (2019–2023). Return on Assets (ROA) averages 9.43% with a standard deviation of 6.53, indicating high profitability variability. Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) has a mean of 0.75 and a standard deviation of 0.56, reflecting a relatively uniform capital structure. Good Corporate Governance (GCG), measured by the number of commissioners and audit committees, averages 7.16 with a standard deviation of 2.10, suggesting stability in corporate governance. Firm size has a mean of 29.52 and a standard deviation of 1.46, indicating consistency within the sample.

B. Model Selection

The model selection process involved the Chow, Hausman, and Lagrange Multiplier (LM) tests. The Chow test yielded a p-value of 0.0000 (<0.05), favoring FEM. The Hausman test produced a p-value of 0.9056 (>0.05), supporting REM. The LM test showed a p-value of 0.0000 (<0.05), confirming REM. Based on these results, the Random Effect Model (REM) was selected as the most suitable model for this study.

C. Classical Assumption Tests

The Classical Assumption Tests included normality, multicollinearity, heteroskedasticity, and autocorrelation tests. The normality test using the Jarque-Bera statistic yielded 201.9408 with a p-value of 0.0000 (<0.05), indicating non-normally distributed residuals. Multicollinearity was assessed by correlation values, with structure capital-ESG at 0.0297315, structure capital-firm size at 0.288369, and ESG-firm size at 0.581987, all below 0.90, confirming no severe multicollinearity. The Glejser test for heteroskedasticity produced a p-value of 0.0897 (>0.05), indicating homoscedasticity. The Durbin-Watson statistic was 1.736063 ($-2 < 1.736063 < 2$), signifying no autocorrelation. These results confirm that the model satisfies classical assumptions, ensuring reliable regression analysis.

D. Regression Testing Results

Panel data regression applies the REM model based on Chow, Hausman, and Lagrange Multiplier tests.

Table V. Multiple Linear Regression Results

Dependent	Variable:			Y
Method:	Panel	Least		Squares
Date:	10/24/24	Time:		01:55
Sample:	2019			2023
Periods	included:			5
Cross-sections	included:			23
Total panel (balanced) observations: 115				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	5.956.054	1.313.116	4.535.818	0.0000
X1	-1.577.908	1.084.077	-1.455.531	0.1483
X2	0.789175	0.339777	2.322.628	0.0220
X3	-1.848.874	0.488124	-3.787.712	0.0002

Source: Eviews Data Processing (2025)

The regression equation is formulated as follows:

$$Y = 59.56054 - 1.577908X_1 + 0.789175X_2 - 1.848874X_3$$

A 1% increase in capital structure (X_1) leads to a 157.79% decline in financial performance, while a 1% increase in ESG (X_2) results in a 78.92% improvement. Conversely, firm size (X_3) exerts a negative impact, where a 1% increase corresponds to a 184.88% reduction in financial performance.

E. Coefficient of Determination

Table VI. Multiple Linear Regression Results

R-squared	0.143542
Adjusted R-squared	0.120395
S.E. of regression	6.127961
Sum squared resid	4168.262
Log likelihood	-369.6215
F-statistic	6.201188
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000620

Source: Eviews Data Processing (2025)

The coefficient of determination (Adjusted R²) is 0.1204 (12.04%), indicating that capital structure, ESG, and firm size explain 12.04% of the variation in financial performance. The remaining 87.96% is influenced by other factors outside the model, highlighting the need for additional variables to improve explanatory power.

F. F-Test

The F-test result shows F-value = 6.2012 > F-table = 2.6864 with a significance level of 0.00062 < 0.05, indicating that capital structure, ESG, and firm size collectively have a significant impact on financial performance. Thus, H₀ is rejected, confirming the joint influence of independent variables on the dependent variable.

G. T-Test

Table VII. Multiple Linear Regression Results

Variable	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	4.535818	0.0000
X1	-1.455531	0.1483
X2	2.322628	0.0220
X3	-3.787712	0.0002

Source: Eviews Data Processing (2025)

The table above presents:

- a. Capital Structure (X1)
The t-value (1.455531) < t-table (1.981180) with a significance of 0.1483 > 0.05, indicating that capital structure has no effect on financial performance.
- b. ESG (X2)
The t-value (2.322628) > t-table (1.981180) with a significance of 0.0220 < 0.05, indicating that ESG positively and significantly affects financial performance.
- c. Firm Size (X3)
The t-value (3.787712) > t-table (1.981180) with a significance of 0.0002 < 0.05, indicating that firm size negatively and significantly affects financial performance.

V. DISCUSSION

A. Effects of Capital Structure on Financial Performance

The t-test results indicate t-value = 1.455531 < t-table = 1.981180 with a significance level of 0.1483 > 0.05, leading to the rejection of H₁, confirming that capital structure has no significant impact on financial performance.

This finding suggests that changes in debt levels do not significantly affect asset returns, as most debt financing is allocated to capital expenditures rather than operational activities. While debt increases interest expenses, it simultaneously reduces taxable income, mitigating its direct impact on corporate profitability. According to capital structure theory, exceeding the optimal debt level elevates financial risk, potentially deteriorating financial performance.

Moreover, financial performance is primarily influenced by working capital efficiency and revenue generation rather than debt repayment obligations. Higher leverage can reduce return on assets and invested capital due to increasing fixed costs, thereby diminishing profitability. This supports the agency theory perspective, where management may not always optimize external and internal funds to maximize shareholder returns.

This study aligns with prior research that found no significant relationship between capital structure and financial performance (Farida & Yulazri, 2024; Harsono & Pamungkas, 2020; Jessica & Triyani, 2022; Sholihah, 2020). Conversely, other studies reported negative (Dahlia, 2018; Indomo, 2019) or positive effects (Alfisah & Zulfikar, 2020; Riswan & Martha, 2024), suggesting that the impact of capital structure is context-dependent and influenced by financial management strategies.

B. Effects of ESG on Financial Performance

The t-test results show $t\text{-value} = 2.322628 > t\text{-table} = 1.981180$ with a significance level of $0.0220 < 0.05$, supporting H_2 , confirming that ESG has a positive and significant impact on financial performance.

Effective ESG implementation enhances corporate reputation, competitiveness, and stakeholder trust. Companies that integrate sustainability governance tend to receive positive responses from customers, employees, and investors, fostering loyalty and increasing demand for their products and services. Transparency and accountability in ESG disclosures further strengthen market confidence, attracting investment and reducing capital costs. Additionally, ESG compliance helps firms manage regulatory and social risks, leading to improved operational efficiency.

Higher market trust in ESG-oriented firms creates greater growth opportunities, expands market share, and boosts profitability. Consequently, firms that embed ESG into their strategic framework gain a competitive advantage that supports long-term financial growth.

This study is consistent with previous research highlighting the positive impact of ESG on financial performance (Ahmad et al., 2021; Buallay, 2019; Melinda & Wardhani, 2020; Prayitno et al., 2024). However, other studies found a negative impact (Duque-Grisales & Aguilera-Caracue, 2019; Rohman et al., 2024; Zahroh & Hersugondo, 2021) or no significant effect (Husada & Handayani, 2021; Junius et al., 2020).

C. Effects of Firm Size on Financial Performance

The t-test results indicate $t\text{-value} = 3.787712 > t\text{-table} = 1.981180$ with a significance level of $0.0002 < 0.05$, confirming H_3 , meaning firm size has a negative and significant impact on financial performance.

Larger firms generally have better access to capital markets, enhancing financial flexibility and securing funding at lower interest rates. However, scale does not always guarantee operational efficiency. Without effective asset management, increasing firm size may reduce financial performance. Higher operating costs—including labor, administration, and asset maintenance—can erode profitability. Moreover, managerial complexity in large firms may hinder strategic decision-making, slowing responses to market dynamics and reducing working capital efficiency.

This study aligns with prior research identifying a negative relationship between firm size and financial performance (Amalia et al., 2021; Harsono & Pamungkas, 2020; Shintia & Yusbardini, 2021). However, other studies found a positive impact (Dahlia, 2018; Indomo, 2019; Riswan & Martha, 2024) or no significant effect (Farida & Yulazri, 2024; Jessica & Triyani, 2022), suggesting that firm size alone does not guarantee superior financial performance.

D. Effects of Capital Structure, ESG, and Firm Size on Financial Performance

The F-test results show $F\text{-value} = 6.201188 > F\text{-table} = 2.686384$ with a significance level of $0.000620 < 0.05$, confirming H_4 , indicating that capital structure, ESG, and firm size collectively have a positive and significant impact on financial performance.

A well-balanced capital structure—integrating both internal and external financing—enhances corporate assets and valuation (Suryaningrum & Ratnawati, 2024). Erawati et al. (2022) suggested that a higher debt proportion can improve financial performance. However, other studies found no significant effect (Farida & Yulazri, 2024; Harsono & Pamungkas, 2020).

Effective ESG practices contribute to financial performance by reinforcing corporate governance, transparency, and investor confidence (Mujiyati, 2020). The audit committee plays a crucial role in ensuring financial reporting integrity through independence (Reni, 2022). Additionally, strong corporate governance enhances financial performance quality (Hidayat et al., 2021).

Firm size is a determinant of financial performance. Larger firms have broader access to funding and can leverage economies of scale to enhance profitability (Jessica & Triyani, 2022). However, research suggests that excessive asset growth may negatively impact financial performance if not accompanied by operational efficiency (Amalia et al., 2021).

Thus, this study confirms that an optimal capital structure, effective corporate governance, and appropriate firm size contribute to enhanced financial performance and corporate competitiveness.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study analyzes the impact of capital structure, ESG, and firm size on financial performance. The findings reveal that capital structure has no significant effect, as debt is primarily allocated for capital expenditures rather than operational needs. While high debt levels increase financial risk, they also provide tax benefits, making their impact on profitability neutral. ESG positively influences financial performance, as companies with strong ESG practices gain higher stakeholder trust, enhanced reputation, and better access to investment opportunities. Transparency in ESG reporting also fosters investor confidence, reducing capital costs and improving operational efficiency. Firm size negatively affects financial performance, as larger firms often struggle with increased operational costs, managerial complexity, and slower decision-making, which reduce profitability. However, firm size can provide advantages such as easier access to financial markets and economies of scale if managed effectively. Simultaneous testing confirms that capital structure, ESG, and firm size significantly influence financial performance, indicating that a well-balanced capital structure, strong ESG implementation, and effective asset utilization are crucial for corporate success. The results highlight the context-dependent nature of financial strategies, where industry characteristics, management effectiveness, and market conditions shape the impact of these variables on firm performance.

REFERENCES

1. Agustina, A. A., Sudaryanti, D., & Alrasyid, H. (2025). Pengaruh Environmental, Social, Governance (Esg) Reporting Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan (Studi Kasus Pada Sektor Manufaktur Dan Jasa Di Bei). *E_Jurnal Ilmiah Riset Akuntansi*, 14(01), 106–117.
2. Amaliyah, F., & Herwiyanti, E. (2020). Pengaruh Keputusan Investasi, Ukuran Perusahaan, Keputusan Pendanaan Dan Kebijakan Dividen Terhadap Nilai Perusahaan Sektor Pertambangan. *Jurnal Penelitian Ekonomi Dan Bisnis*, 5(1), 39–51. <https://doi.org/10.33633/jpeb.v5i1.2783>
3. Amelinda, T. N., & Rachmawati, L. (2021). Pengaruh Penerapan Good Corporate Governance Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan Bank Umum Syariah Di Indonesia. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 4(1), 33–44. <https://journal.unesa.ac.id/index.php/jei/article/download/11619/5387>
4. Aprilianti, W., & Sisdianto, E. (2024). Pengaruh Faktor Fundamental Terhadap Harga Saham Pada Kinerja Keuangan Perusahaan Yang Terdaftar Di Bursa Efek Indonesia (Bei). *Jurnal Bisnis Kreatif Dan Inovatif*, 1(2), 33–43. <https://doi.org/10.61132/jubikin.v1i2.90>
5. Humas, S. K. R. I. (2021). *Sekretariat Kabinet Republik Indonesia | Menperin: Sektor Manufaktur Bertahan Dan Tumbuh Saat Dihantam Pandemi*.
6. Injayanti, S. O., Maemumah, M., & Lukita, C. (2020). Pengaruh Good Corporate Governance Dan Ukuran Perusahaan Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan. *Kia : Konferensi Ilmiah Akuntansi X*, 1–13.
7. Jao, R., Tangke, P., Holly, A., Loandy, B. K., Atma, U., Makassar, J., Tanjung, J., No, A., 23, S., & Selatan, I. (2022). Peran Mekanisme Good Corporate Governance Dalam Meningkatkan Reputasi Perusahaan Serta Dampaknya Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan. *Assets : Jurnal Ekonomi, Manajemen Dan Akuntansi*, 12(1), 138–158. <https://doi.org/10.24252/assets.v1i1.27907>
8. Kurniawati, H., Rasyid, R., & Setiawan, F. A. (2020). Pengaruh Intellectual Capital Dan Ukuran Perusahaan Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan Perusahaan. *Jurnal Muara Ilmu Ekonomi Dan Bisnis*, 4(1), 64–76.
9. Laksono, B. S., & Kusumaningias, R. (2021). Pengaruh Good Corporate Governance Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan Dan Nilai Perusahaan Sektor Aneka Industri Tahun 2016-2018. *Akunesa: Jurnal Akuntansi Unesa*, 09(02).
10. Mahdi, S., & Rahmawati, M. I. (2023). Pengaruh Kinerja Keuangan Terhadap Respon Investor Perusahaan Food And Beverage Yang Terdaftar Di Bei. *Jurnal Ilmu Dan Riset Akuntansi (Jira)*, 12(4), 1–20.

11. Mulia, C. (2021). Faktor-Faktor Yang Memengaruhi Kinerja Keuangan Perusahaan Manufaktur Industri Makanan Dan Minuman Di Bei Periode 2017-2019. *Jurnal Akuntansi*, 10(1), 63–74. <https://doi.org/10.46806/Ja.V10i1.799>
12. Ngantung, V. A., & Handoyo, S. E. (2023). Pengaruh Struktur Modal, Gcg, Dan Ukuran Perusahaan Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan Perusahaan Farmasi. *Jurnal Manajerial Dan Kewirausahaan*, 5(1), 66–75. <https://doi.org/10.24912/Jmk.V5i1.22514>
13. Nilawati, A., & Hendrani, A. (2024). Pengaruh Ukuran Perusahaan, Leverage, Dan Likuiditas Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan. *Journal Of Economic, Bussines And Accounting (Costing)*, 7(3), 5502–5518. <https://doi.org/10.31539/Costing.V7i3.9256>
14. Ningsih, S., & Utami, W. B. (2020). Pengaruh Operating Leverage Dan Struktur Modal Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan Pada Perusahaan Go Publik Sektor Property Dan Real Estate. *Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Pajak*, 20(2), 154–160.
15. Pertiwi, J. C., Oktavia, R., & Amelia, Y. (2023). Analisis Perbandingan Metode Pendeteksian Kecurangan Keuangan Menggunakan Altman Z-Score, Beneish M-Score, Dan Springate. *Fair Value: Jurnal Ilmiah Akuntansi Dan Keuangan*, 5(6), 2666–2676. <https://doi.org/10.32670/Fairvalue.V5i6.2534>
16. Putri, Aulia D., & Rafli, R. (2024). *Pengaruh Struktur Modal Dan Ukuran Perusahaan Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan Dengan Good Corporate Governance Sebagai Variabel Moderasi (Studi Pada Perusahaan Manufaktur Industri Pariwisata Dan Rekreasi Yang Terdaftar Di Bursa Efek Indonesia Tahun 2020 - 2022*.
17. Rahman, Karlina Ghazalah S. (2020). *Good Governance Dan Pengendalian Internal Pada Kinerja Pengelolaan Keuangan: Teori Dan Praktek* (Nur Kholik (Ed.); Pertama). Edu Publisher.
18. Rombe, Y. (Yusuf), & Sintha, L. (Lis). (2023). *Kinerja Keuangan Di Masa Pandemi Covid-19* (B. W. B. Persada (Ed.)). Cv Widina Media Utama.
19. Senastri, Khaula. (2023). *Kinerja Keuangan: Pengertian, Penilaian Dan Fungsinya Bagi Sebuah Bisnis*. Accurate.
20. Wijaya, I., Rate, P. V., & Maramis, J. B. (2023). Komparasi Kinerja Keuangan Perusahaan Sektor Food And Beverages Yang Terdaftar Di Bursa Efek Indonesia Sebelum Dan Sesaat Pandemi Covid-19 Comparison Of Financial Performance Of Food And Beverages Sector Companies Listed On The Stock Exchange Indonesia Be. *390 Jurnal Emba*, 11(3), 390–397.

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